

Sickle Cell Disease Its Occurrences and Treatment: A Review

Dr P K Patra^{1,2}, Dr Ashish Patel*², Dr Prashant Nigam³, Dr Kshitiz Verma², Dr M K Verma²

1. Research Scholar CSVTU Bhilai (CG)
2. Chhattisgarh Swami Vivekanand Technical University Bhilai (CG)
3. Chhattisgarh Institute of Medical Sciences, Bilaspur (CG)

Abstract- Sickle cell disease, also known as sickle cell anemia, is a genetic disorder characterized by abnormal hemoglobin in the red blood cells, leading to their sickle or crescent shape. This condition can cause various complications such as pain, anemia, organ damage, and increased susceptibility to infections.

In Chhattisgarh, a state in central India, sickle cell disease is a significant health concern. The state has a high prevalence of this genetic disorder, primarily among tribal communities. Factors such as limited healthcare infrastructure, lack of awareness, and socio-economic challenges contribute to the burden of the disease in the region.

Efforts are being made by the government and various organizations to address sickle cell disease in Chhattisgarh through initiatives such as screening programs, genetic counseling, and access to proper medical care. However, more comprehensive strategies are needed to effectively manage and reduce the impact of the disease on the affected population.

Keywords- sickle cell disease, β -globin gene, mutation,

I- INTRODUCTION:

Herrick originally described sickle cell disease (SCD) in 1910. The β -globin gene mutation results in both homozygous and compound heterozygote inheritance.[1] In the sixth position of the β -chain of haemoglobin, known as haemoglobin S (HbS), a single base-pair point mutation (GAG to GTG) results in the replacement of the amino acid glutamic acid, which is hydrophilic, for valine, which is hydrophobic.[2] Despite a clearly defined Mendelian inheritance, phenotypic variation in clinical presentation is a distinctive feature of sickle cell disease (SCD). This mutation was first molecularly characterized and described by Pauling [3] and was later confirmed to be caused by a single amino acid substitution, specifically valine, by Ingram [3] nearly 70 years ago. SCD is a multi-organ, multi-system illness that manifests as both acute and chronic problems. By the time a child is five to six months old, his foetal haemoglobin (HbF) has decreased to an adult level. [4] Sickle cell disease is one of the most prevalent autosomal genetic illnesses. It is the most serious type of regular hemoglobinopathy.

Different illnesses varying in severity of anaemia, recurrence of emergencies, and survival rate can be brought about by sickle cell disease (SCD).[5] The practically symptomless sickle cell trait gives rise to the potentially fatal condition known as sickle cell anaemia due to variations in its clinical severity. Individuals diagnosed with sickle cell disease (SCD) have a wide spectrum of haemoglobin phenotypic structures, ranging from minor vaso-occlusive crisis to severe clinical symptoms. WHO statistics and data indicate that millions of people worldwide are afflicted with SCD. Because sickle cell disease confers malaria resistance on its carrier, it is recommended that sickle cell disease (SCD) be common in malaria endemic areas.

People with African, Mediterranean (Greece, Turkey and Italy), Arabian Peninsula, Indian, and Spanish-speaking regions of South America, Central America, and some Caribbean islands ancestry are more likely to suffer from SCD. One faulty β -globin gene is inherited by people with sickle cell

trait (SCT). However, in contrast to sickle cell disease, the other β -globin chain is untouched, meaning that it keeps its phenotypic and functional characteristics. Because of this, those who have sickle cell trait typically have minimal anaemia or show no symptoms at all, which lessens the disease's skeletal presentation. [6][7]

Traditionally, sickle cell therapy (SCT) has been viewed as a non-disease state, benign illness without the painful episodes typical of homozygous SCD. Population-based SCT has no discernible effect on life expectancy. Over 300 million people worldwide carry the sickle cell trait, with sub-Saharan Africa having the highest incidence of between 30% and 40%.[5] One of the oldest ethnic groups of native people living in the Terai region of Nepal are the Tharu people. WHO stated in 1990 that the majority of Tharu groups in western Nepal were affected by various hemoglobinopathies, with sickle cell disease being the most frequent genetic illness in this group? A range of liver abnormalities may manifest as detrimental effects in patients with sickle cell anemia/trait.

This is because liver dysfunction in sickle cell disease is multifactorial [8] and the complications of liver dysfunction are significant and in most cases fatal. [9] Confirmation of sickle cell liver disease is obtained either by abnormal biochemical tests or from a postmortem liver biopsy specimen, rarely from an antemortem liver specimen.

Sickle cell anemia (SCD) damages the red blood cells that produce hemoglobin S (Hgb S). In physiologically stressful environments (ie, lack of oxygen, acidity, extreme cold), polymerization of HbS causes RBC sickling. This deformation leads to vaso-occlusive crises, hemolysis, reduced nitroxide bioavailability, inflammation, endothelial damage, and activation of leukocytes and platelets.[10] Vaso-occlusive crisis can occur in any tissue, usually in the lung, brain, bone, kidney and spleen.[11] Less commonly, sickle cell crisis in the liver can lead to hepatopathy, a well-defined but rare disease. Sickle cell disease is complex and is usually caused by multiple factors at once. [8]

In sickle cell anemia, comorbidities such as chronic blood transfusion, alcoholism, acute and chronic hepatitis B and C infection are often associated with the development of liver disease. Hepatopathy in patients with sickle cell anemia can have both acute and severe manifestations, such as liver sequestration, vascular occlusion, acute ischemia and cholestasis can all lead to acute liver failure, and it is very important to recognize this condition and start appropriate treatment. [8, 12, 13] In developed countries, SCD is a debilitating chronic disease with significant morbidity due to major organ damage. The liver is one of the affected organs resulting in sickle cell hepatopathy. Some end-organ damage in SCD has a well-recognized natural history with reinforcement-based treatment algorithms: it is associated with kidney disease, cardiopulmonary disease, and cerebrovascular disease (in children).

However, the natural history and pathogenesis of liver disease are not well characterized, and the rationale for intervention is uncertain, despite end-organ damage being a compelling cause of morbidity and mortality.[9][13] Liver disorders are common but are often thought to be limited to gallstones. Gallstone disease is very common and can cause serious complications, but acute and chronic liver disease, commonly known as "sickle cell liver disease", is increasingly recognized as a cause of serious symptoms, even death. Chronic biliary disease is another, more serious problem resulting from a combination of chronic ischemia and immune-mediated damage, which may be associated with genetic susceptibility. Iron overload from repeated blood transfusions and especially hepatotoxicity from iron chelators is also a concern, although rare in childhood. Blood hepatitis B and C are rare in Western countries, but continue to be an essential comorbidity in poor countries. Transaminases, alkaline phosphatase (AP) and gamma-glutamyltransferase (G-GT) were most often considered indicators of hepatobiliary disease. Increased serum transaminases (AST and ALT) usually indicate hepatocellular damage.[17] Cholestasis increases serum alkaline phosphatase

and G-GT activity. The most common diagnosis in asymptomatic patients with otherwise detected transaminase elevations, usually mild to moderate, are: alcoholic liver disease, (mostly chronic) viral hepatitis, and much less often drug-induced liver disease and non-alcoholic steatosis. [14]

The initial documentation of sickle cell anemia occurred within indigenous communities in South India [1], subsequently spreading to Central India [2]. The prevalence of sickle cell trait across India stands at 4.3% [2]. In specific regions such as Orissa and Chhattisgarh, the occurrence of sickle cell disease is notably higher, estimated at around 9% and 10% respectively [3, 4]. Chhattisgarh, which separated from southeastern Madhya Pradesh in 2000, is home to a population where 32% have tribal roots [4].

II- HISTORY OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

The signs associated with sickle cell crises have been regarded by various names in Africa, long before they were diagnosed within the western world. [14] Symptoms of sickle cell anemia can be traced returned to year 1670 in a single Ghanian family.[15] It changed into in 1910 when James Herrick [1] found, “odd elongated sickle shaped RBCs” present in the blood of an anaemic black scientific scholar, after which the medical community came to know approximately it. It turned into the discovery of Emmel [16] in 1917 of the sickling phenomena in vitro, in the individuals of a family which first recommended the genetic foundation for sickling. So, it turned into observed to be an inheritable circumstance. Subsequently, it changed into explained that the sickling phenomenon, in vitro, turned into due to deprivation of oxygen. [17] Each Huck and Sydenstricker, who did the special analysis of the pedigrees of Huck's patients, concluded that the sickle mobile phenomenon became inherited as a Mendelian autosomal recessive function. Within the two separate researches [18], heterozygous kingdom for sickle gene in sickling positives without large symptoms and homozygous kingdom for sickle gene in symptomatic individuals have been hooked up. Inside the equal year the unusual gradual fee of migration of sickle hemoglobin on electrophoresis was observed. [19] The difference in amino acid series in one part of polypeptide chain of Hb S turned into confirmed in the later years.[20] due to the fact that then, there was a rapid growth of facts approximately sickle cellular ailment and it's miles still unfolding.

III- ORIGIN OF SICKLE GENE

The single mutation theory proposed that a mutation occurred in Neolithic times in the fertile Arabian Peninsula [21]. As the climate changed and the region turned into a desert, people carrying the gene migrated to India, Eastern Saudi Arabia, and Equatorial regions.

Initially, a single mutation theory was suggested, in which it was conveyed that a single mutation was occurred in Neolithic times in the then fertile Arabian Peninsula.[21] Then, due to changing climatic conditions and conversion of this region to a desert led the migration of people that could have carried the gene to India, Eastern Saudi Arabia and down to Equatorial.

In the context of Africa, it was previously theorized that the sickle cell gene mutation was linked to specific agricultural practices and supported by anthropological evidence. However, it is now evident that the development of the sickle cell gene mutation occurred independently in various circumstances. Through the use of different restriction endonucleases, distinct chromosome structures (haplotypes) have been identified; with the Hb S gene being associated with different haplotypes compared to the Hb A gene [22]. In Africa, the Hb S gene is linked to at least three haplotypes - the Benin, Senegal, and Central African Republic (Bantu) haplotypes, found in different regions of Africa. Additionally, an Asian haplotype has been identified in Saudi Arabia and central India. The presence of region-specific haplotypes suggests that the mutant beta globin

gene emerged separately in these locations [23]. These regions are now endemic to malaria, indicating that the high prevalence of the sickle mutation is a result of natural selection [24]. The mutation causing sickle hemoglobin occurs gradually, with individuals carrying one sickle hemoglobin gene and one normal hemoglobin gene (sickle cell trait) showing greater resistance to malaria than those with two normal hemoglobin genes.

The generally accepted theory states that HbS provides selective protection against falciparum malaria, most likely due to P.F.'s induction of sickling, which occurs even at physiological oxygen tension. This is followed by the sequestration of parasitized red cells deep within the reticuloendothelial system, where the microenvironment is unfavourable for the growth of the parasite.[25] Consequently, individuals that possess sickle cell trait would be more likely to survive a malaria outbreak and pass on their genes (sickle and normal haemoglobin) to their offspring. Most commonly accepted theory of balanced polymorphism is assumed to be responsible for the remarkable stability of sickle gene in Africa, which allows it to persist at a relatively sustained level in a population without being removed. [26]

The widely accepted hypothesis is that HbS gives selective prevention against falciparum malaria probably because of induction of sickling occurring even at physiological oxygen tension by P.F. which is followed by sequestration of parasitized red cells deep within reticuloendothelial system where microenvironment is malicious for parasite growth.[25] Therefore, people with sickle cell trait would have a better likelihood of surviving an outbreak of malaria and passing their genes (sickle and normal hemoglobin) to the next generation when they have children. The phenomenal stability of sickle gene in Africa which allows it to remain at a relatively sustained level in a population without being eliminated is thought to be because of most widely accepted hypothesis of balanced polymorphism. [26] In India, sickle cell disease is primarily seen in tribal communities, who are still largely cut off from the mainstream of society. It seems unlikely that the presence of a sickle cell gene from a non-Indian source occurred to the extent necessary to explain the up to 35% heterozygosity rates observed in some tribes. Although available data prevents a definitive response, migration and trade seem to be the more plausible routes for gene flow from India to the Persian Gulf region. Here, sickle cell disease affects the offspring of Africans who travelled to India in the era of the moguls, frequently serving as the Indian princes' "praetorian guards."

IV- PREVALENCE OF SICKLE GENE IN TRIBAL COMMUNITIES IN INDIA

The world's biggest concentration of tribal people is found in India. They are believed to have been the first settlers in the nation and are thought to have arrived early. According to the 2011 Census of India [27], 8.6% of India's total population, or 67.8 million individuals, were classified as tribal. Approximately 83% of the nation's scheduled tribe population resides in the states of M.P., Maharashtra, Odisha, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal, and Karnataka, with the majority of these tribal communities being rural residents. There are 461 scheduled tribes in all, and they all have distinct social structures, dialects, and cultural patterns that they generally keep to themselves. Still, Reich et al. [28]. a time of widespread intermarriage that occurred "several thousand years ago throughout the subcontinent, intermixing its population's genetic deck so properly that it left clear reflectance even in the genomes of today's most isolated tribes," the paper stated.

Lehman and Cutbush acknowledged that sickle haemoglobin was first identified in India in 1952 in the indigenous tribes of the Nilgiris highlands in southern India. The existence of sickle haemoglobin was also introduced by Dunlop and Mazumdar in the same year in the Upper Assamese tea garden workforce, who was primarily migrant labourers from tribal communities in Bihar and Odisha. [29] Subsequently, a wide range of population groups have been studied, and it has been shown that the sickle cell gene is common in three socioeconomically disadvantaged

ethnic groups in India: scheduled tribes, scheduled castes, and other backward classes. There is variation in the prevalence of sickle cell carriers across various ethnic groups, ranging from 1 to 40%. [30] With a computed total of 9, 61,492 sickle heterozygotes and 67,861 sickle homozygotes, Madhya Pradesh state has the highest burden. [31] Nonetheless, the sickle cell belt covers 27 out of 45 districts in Madhya Pradesh, and the prevalence of HbS varies greatly, ranging from 10 to 33 percent. Additionally, it has been projected that 13,432 pregnancies in this state will carry a chance of producing a child with sickle cell disease, and 3358 sickle homozygous births are anticipated each year. [32] The two major tribal communities in central India are the Bhils and the Gonds. The eastern districts of Maharashtra, popularly known as the Vidarbha region, the northern Satpura ranges, and certain areas of Marathwada are all affected by the sickle gene. The percentage of sickle cell carriers varies between 0 and 35 percent across various tribes. Tribal groups Bhils, Madias, Pawaras, Pardhans, and Otkars have significant HbS prevalence (20–35%). Additionally, it has been reported that there are over 5,000 cases of sickle cell anaemia spread across the districts of Gadchiroli, Chandrapur, Nagpur, Bhandara, Yoetmal, and Nandurbar. [33]

V- SICKLE CELL HEMOGLOBIN

For thousands of years, sickle cell haemoglobin (HbS) has been present in humans. Ghanaian physician Dr. Konotey-Ahulu noticed that clinical symptoms that were identifiable as sickle cell anaemia were given distinct names by West African tribes. However, Chicago physician Robert Herrick discovered sickle cells for the first time in 1910 when testing an anaemic West Indian patient's peripheral blood. While homozygous sickle cell anaemia is the most prevalent and dangerous kind of sickle cell disease (SCD), there are other sickling disorders that link haemoglobin S to haemoglobin C, haemoglobin D, beta or alpha thalassemia, and other haemoglobins that have a similar pathophysiology but distinct clinical features. A single base pair mutation in the gene encoding the adult haemoglobin beta-globin polypeptide chain causes HbS. A change in the sixth codon from adenine to thymine, which substitute's valine for glutamic acid at the sixth amino acid position in the beta-globin chain. The electrophoretically different haemoglobin that Linus Pauling described in 1949 is captured by this substitution. [37] When HbS is deoxygenated, the beta-6 valine hides in a hydrophobic pocket on a nearby beta-globin chain, fusing the molecules to create intractable polymers. These insoluble polymers produce the conventional sickle shape when present in sufficient amounts. The red blood cell membrane is severely destroyed by this process. Following the clustering of sickled red blood cells, microvascular blockage resulted. Additionally, these aberrant sickle red blood cells interact with different cytokines and attach to endothelium cells [38].

The foundation of SCD pathophysiology is the process of microthrombosis and microembolization. Sickled erythrocytes block the microvasculature, resulting in severe crises, priapism, pulmonary emboli, osteonecrosis, and eventually harm to all organ systems, including the kidneys, liver, spleen, and retina. Many SCD patients have chronic reticulocytosis and haemoglobin levels between 20% and 35%. Fever, infections, high levels of physical activity, temperature swings, hypoxia, and hypertonic solutions can all hasten the onset of clinical symptoms. The expression of additional haemoglobin, endothelial factors, nitric oxide, and other variables, as well as the concentration of HbS in red blood cells, all influence how clinically significant the symptoms are. Additionally, the number of dense, dehydrated erythrocytes is higher in SCD patients. The replacement of valine for glutamic acid hardly affects the oxygenated form of haemoglobin S. [39]

The red blood cell is distorted into a sickle shape as a result of the production of insoluble fibres and bundles caused by deoxygenated haemoglobin S, which has distinct features from deoxygenated haemoglobin A when its concentration is sufficiently high. The biology and clinical symptomatology of sickle cell disease (SCD) have been steadily uncovered since the discovery of HbS. [40] Anaemia and four forms of crises—painful (Vaso occlusive), sequestrative, hemolytic,

and aplastic—are prevalent in sickle cell disease (SCD). Damage to the membrane of red blood cells results in decreased cell viability and persistent hemolytic anaemia. This damage raises the risk of heart failure, stroke, and the production of bilirubin gallstones is dangerous enough.

Additionally, sickled red blood cells provide mechanical impedance to blood flow that exacerbates anaemia and increases the risk of widespread Vaso occlusive consequences. It is interesting to note that anaemia can, in part, protect against consequences related to Vaso occlusive disease by reducing the rise in viscosity caused by microcirculation sickling. Therefore, it is recommended to use cautious exchange transfusion therapy and blood transfusion in order to prevent stroke, pulmonary hypertension, pain crises, and other related disorders. In addition to helping blood transport more oxygen, blood transfusions also reduce the proportion of cells capable of causing sickling. For a posttransfusion haematocrit of roughly 36%, it is recommended that transfusion be performed using phenotypically matched, leuko-reduced, sickle-cell-negative blood.[41] There has been extensive research on the side effects of transfusion, which include iron overload, allo- and autoimmunization, and the spread of infectious illnesses including HIV and hepatitis. Additionally, a sizable number of sickle cell anaemia patients have undergone successful bone marrow transplants globally.[42] The procedure is only allowed for certain patients. Even back then, graft-versus-host disease was the main cause of the 5% to 10% death rate associated with bone marrow transplantation. Increasing foetal haemoglobin (HbF) synthesis has been one method of mitigating the effects of HbS polymer formation. It has long been accepted via population and clinical observation that lower blood HbF levels are correlated with less SCD clinical symptoms. It has been suggested since the middle of the 1950s that pharmacological intervention on HbF may have an impact on sickling syndromes. Several agents have been tried up to this point, but hydroxyurea has shown to be the safest and most effective. It's still unclear exactly how hydroxyurea increases the synthesis of HbF. Furthermore, hydroxyurea has been linked to the synthesis of nitric acid, a powerful endothelium relaxing agent, according to current research. C-reactive protein (CRP) is one of many inflammatory markers linked to endothelium surfaces and white blood cells that are elevated in sickle cell disease (SCD). Granulocyte levels at baseline are frequently high. The condition of leucocytosis itself increases mortality risk. [43] Lastly, sickled red blood cells produce much more laminin than normal red blood cells do. Laminin is a component of the endothelium matrix that binds to the Lutheran antigen on red blood cells. In SCD, nearly every aspect of hemostasis that leads to hypercoagulability has been documented. However, it's unclear if the hypercoagulability contributes to or results from the vaso occlusive crisis. Hyposplenism is causing thrombocytosis and increasing platelet aggregation. Protein C and S levels may drop and antiphospholipid antibodies may rise. Furthermore, elevated levels of factor VIII and von Willebrand factor may arise. Heparin, coumadin, and antiplatelet medicines are now undergoing restricted therapeutic studies, which have been limited due to equivocal data.

FIGURE 2: SICKLE CELL RED BLOOD CELL ^[44]

VI- SICKLE CELL TRAIT

A person with sickle cell trait (SCT), a benign disorder, carries only one aberrant haemoglobin beta gene allele. On the other hand, sickle cell disease (SCD) is characterised by two aberrant haemoglobin beta gene alleles in the affected person. Patients with SCT typically have a higher quality of life than those with SCD since they do not experience sickling symptoms. This is in contrast to those with SCD. Comparing patients with SCT to the general population, there is no higher risk of death. Hb S, also known as sickle haemoglobin, is the aberrant form of haemoglobin that causes sickle cell trait. A point mutation in the beta globin chain causes sickle haemoglobin. This point mutation causes the beta haemoglobin chain's codon 6 to change from A to T. As a result, the amino acid valine replaces glutamic acid. Red blood cells with haemoglobin of the valine type sickle when their oxygen threshold is lowered. A patient with sickle cell trait is heterozygous, inherited HbS from one parent and HbA from the other. People of African descent and those whose ancestors originated in tropical and subtropical regions where malaria is endemic are more likely to have sickle cell trait. In US, the prevalence of sickle cell trait is 0.2% among Caucasians and 9% among African Americans, or roughly 3 million people.[45] A third of the 300 million individuals thought to have sickle cell trait worldwide reside in sub-Saharan Africa. In regions where malaria is endemic, sickle cell trait is more common. According to Gibson and colleagues, the prevalence can reach 25% in certain regions of Africa and 60% in Saudi Arabia.[45] The number of instances with sickle cell trait and disease will rise in the western region of the world due to migration from high-prevalence regions such as Africa and the Middle East. Vaso-occlusive crisis, which is primarily seen in sickle cell illness, is not brought on by sickle cell trait. However, if a patient has a predisposition to factors that promote sickling, they may present similarly to sickle cell anaemia. Severe hypoxia, dehydration, elevated sympathetic output, hypo- or hyperthermia, elevated 2, 3-DPG levels, and inflammatory cell discharge are risk factors. After that, sickled red blood cells from the HbS will clog small capillary veins, mostly in the bones. In addition to the sickling of the cells, platelets and inflammatory cells also interact with one another to increase the adherence of red blood cells. The body's organs that are susceptible to this include the kidneys, lungs, abdomen, heart, and limbs. Repeated attacks can lead to persistent ischemia, which can harm organs. Under a microscope, red blood cells of sickle cell trait carriers appear normal when they are at rest.

However, red blood cells that are subjected to oxidative stress manifest as sickle cells, or drepanocytes. If there is severe sickling, reticulocytosis might also occur. Patients with sickle cell trait do not have crises like those with sickle cell illness. Most of the time, they don't show any symptoms. They present similarly to hemoglobin-normal patients. It is possible that they have a positive family history of HbSS. Patients with sickle cell trait may present with rhabdomyolysis and haematuria. Patients with sickle cell trait typically don't need any medical intervention. Only when a patient exhibits symptoms, especially those linked to the characteristic, is treatment recommended. In order to begin timely treatment as soon as patients exhibit symptoms, doctors must be aware of the difficulties related to sickle cell trait. For example, it is crucial to rule out papillary necrosis in sickle cell trait individuals presenting with haematuria, and these patients should get conservative therapy. Beta-thalassemia major and minor, as well as various forms of sickle cell disease, are examples of differential diagnosis for sickle cell trait. Patients with sickle cell trait have a good prognosis, despite the fact that the trait has been linked to numerous consequences, including exercise-induced mortality, splenic infarction, asymptomatic bacteriuria, and papillary necrosis. According to Tsaras G. and colleagues' article, patients with sickle cell trait will typically live the same amount of time as the normal population, despite the problems that come with the trait. [46] Even while sickle cell trait is thought to be benign, individuals who carry it are more likely to experience clinical and medical issues. It presents as asymptomatic bacteriuria in female patients, renal papillary necrosis-related haematuria, splenic infarction, renal medullary

cancer, chronic kidney disease, and exertional-related mortality.[47] One of the crucial side effects that has been noted in numerous case studies is papillary necrosis. Patients with sickle cell trait who have an average HbS level of 34% or higher are more likely than those with a HbS level of 20% to exhibit papillary necrosis. Sickle haemoglobin buildup in the kidney's small capillaries or vasa recta can result in microthrombus development and subsequent infarction, which is what causes necrosis. Individuals who have papillary necrosis typically have stomach pain and extensive haematuria as symptoms. Conservative measures such as bed rest, IV fluids, and pain control are typically used in treatment. Because there is usually enough surviving tissue and only one afflicted papillary, the prognosis is usually very good.

VII- GENETICS OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

As previously indicated, early research conducted by Pauling et al. suggested that a haemoglobin molecule deficiency causes sickle cell disease. [37] The disease's autosomal recessive mode of inheritance was discovered that same year. A few years later, Ingram et al. identified the sickle mutation as a glutamine-to-valine change at the sixth position of the b-globin polypeptide. [48] After many years, the human globin genes were cloned, their DNA sequences were analysed, the arrangement of the globin gene clusters was depicted, and a significant amount of knowledge was gained regarding the processes governing their controlled expression. A distinct gene family code for each of the two pairs of identical polypeptide subunits that make up the tetrameric molecule that is haemoglobin in humans. Chromosome 16 has the human α -like globin genes (ζ , $\alpha 1$, and $\alpha 2$), while chromosome 11 contains the β -like globin genes (ϵ , Gg, Ag, d, and b).

The enormous interest in understanding the molecular underpinnings of the transition from foetal to adult haemoglobin production can be attributed to the possibility of therapeutically reactivating HbF production in adulthood. The FDA approved the use of hydroxyurea in the treatment of sickle cell disease patients as a result of research in this area, which was recently discussed [50]. The most prevalent and severe kind of sickle cell disease is caused by homozygosity for the sickle mutation, often known as HbSS illness. The interconnection of various mutations in the human β -globin genes leads to the emergence of many genetic variations of sickle cell disease. The result of the interaction between the βS and βC genes is the usually very mild condition known as HbSC. The outcome of sickling disorder coming from a βS gene interacting with a β -thalassemia gene (a mutant b-globin gene that either cannot produce normal b-globin mRNA or produces it at significantly lower levels) is determined by the severity of the co-inherited β -thalassemia mutation. $S\beta 0$ -thalassemia, whose severity is comparable to homozygous HbSS illness, results from the co-inherited b-thalassaemia gene going fully inactive ($b 0$ -thalassaemia). [51]

FIGURE: 3: Chromosomal organization of the alpha and beta globin gene clusters ^[49]

On the other hand, $S\beta^+$ -thalassemia can have a wide range of clinical severity when the coinherited β -thalassemia gene is determined to be partially active, resulting in β^+ -thalassemia. Clinically mild $S\beta^+$ -thalassemia usually results from mild β^+ -thalassemia mutations, which are frequent in people of African origin. On the other hand, clinical sickling condition will be moderate if the β^+ -thalassemia mutation is more severe, as is frequently the case in Mediterranean populations. [52].

VIII- RISK FACTORS

There are two million sickle cell trait carriers in the world. The majority of carriers do not exhibit any symptoms, and their sickle haemoglobin (HbS) percentage is minimal. Sickle cell illness can arise via the transfer of the sickle cell trait from two carriers to their progeny. Every pregnancy carries a 50% probability of producing two children with sickle cell trait and a 25% likelihood of the child developing sickle cell illness. Black people or those of African descent make up the majority of sickle cell disease patients in the United States. 1. The sickle cell trait affects about 1 in 13 Black or African American newborns. 2. One Black or African American baby out of every 365 is affected with sickle cell disease. Sickle cell disease affects a large number of persons with Hispanic, Southern European, Middle Eastern, and Asian Indian ancestry. In the United States, approximately a million people suffer with sickle cell disease.

FIGURE: 4: Sickle cell disorder inheritance pattern^[53]

A - PREDISPOSING FACTORS FOR SICKLE CELL CRISIS

1. Contaminations
2. Insufficient oxygen tension
3. Coexisting medical disease (such as herpes, diabetes, or sarcoidosis)
4. Lack of fluids
5. Acidemia
6. Vigorous physical activity
7. Tobacco
8. Maternity
9. chilly conditions

IX- CO-INHERITANCE OF SICKLE GENE WITH OTHER Hb DEFECTS

In 1944, the compound heterozygosity (β_s/β_{thal}) for the sickle gene and β -thalassaemia gene was first introduced by Silvestroni and Bianco [53]. Since then, cases of HbS- β thalassaemia have been reported from various Indian ethnic groups. In addition to hemoglobinopathy (HbS), β -thalassaemia is also common in some tribal populations; in some tribes from Gujarat and Odisha, the frequency can reach 6–14%. [54] However, there aren't many documented examples of HbS- β -thalassaemia among indigenous communities. Mukherjee et al. revealed seven cases in 2010 (ages 7 to 21)[55]. They only occasionally experienced modest episodes of vaso-occlusive crises or were asymptomatic. The β^0 mutation, codon 15(G>A), and concomitant α -thalassaemia were present in all of them. Previous research from Odisha revealed that the IVS 1-5 (G→C) mutation is linked to the presence of HbS- β^+ -thalassaemia. The HbA levels in these instances were modest (3–5%). The occasional disclosure of HbS co-existence with HbD Punjab, HbE, and HbC has also been revealed due to movement for job and some relationship over the years.

X- CO-INHERITANCE OF SICKLE CELL GENE WITH G6PD DEFICIENCY

G6PD deficiency often has no discernible impact on sickle cell anaemia patients. However, concurrent G6PD deficiency worsens anaemia and raises the need for blood transfusions in infancy and early childhood up to the age of two, but has minimal effect beyond that point, according to a new study. [57] G6PD deficiency is highly prevalent among Indian tribal communities. Random screening was conducted for haemoglobin variants and G6PD deficiency in a cross-section of 15 major tribal communities from various regions of Odisha. High frequencies of sickle cell hemoglobinopathy (0-22.4%) and G6PD deficiency (4.3-17.4%) were noted, with 12 individuals developing both disorders. [57] Within the fourteen primordial tribal groups that originated in four distinct States and reported a high incidence of sickle cell gene, the prevalence of G6PD deficiency

ranged from 0.7 to 15.6%. [58] As a result, testing for G6PD deficiency may be essential in newborn sickle cell disease screening programmes.

XI- PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

As An autosomal-recessive hereditary condition known as sickle cell disease affects millions of people globally and about a million people in the United States. A comprehensive review of the Global Burden of illness Study [59] found that each year, 176,000 people die from problems related to sickle cell illness, 43 million individuals have sickle cell trait, and 3.2 million people have sickle cell disease. All mutations in the β -globin gene that cause the same clinical condition are collectively referred to as sickle cell disease (SCD). The most prevalent type of sickle cell disease, sickle cell anaemia accounts for 70% of occurrences among patients with African ancestry. The beta-S (β S) allele, which is found on chromosome 11p15.5, is homozygous for sickle cell anaemia.

It differs from the wild-type β -allele by a single nucleotide polymorphism (dbSNP (T; T) in which GAG is substituted for GTG at the sixth codon of the β -globin gene. [60] This causes a hydrophobic valine residue (Val) to replace a hydrophilic glutamic acid residue (Glu) at the sixth position in the β -globin chain. As a result, sickle cell anaemia sufferers' red blood cells have a mutant haemoglobin tetramer, or HbS (α 2 β S2). [61] Different forms of sickle cell disease are caused by multiple interconnected molecular and cellular mechanisms, such as homozygous acquisition of the β S mutation (HbSS) or coinheritance of β S with other mutations, such as β C (HbSC), β D (HbSD), β O (HbSO/Arab), β E (HbSE), or a β -thalassemia allele (HbS/ β -thal0 or HbS/ β -thal+). The image below illustrates how, over the course of the last seven decades, researchers have identified three main pathobiological processes that lead to clinical disease: hemolysis-mediated endothelial dysfunction, vaso-occlusion, and HbS polymerization. More recently, sterile inflammation has emerged as a fourth pathway.

FIGURE 5: Molecular pathophysiology of sickle cell disease^[62]

XII- SICKLE CELL HEPATOPATHY

In patients with sickle cell disease (SCD), a range of liver diseases resulting from diverse liver injuries are referred to as sickle cell hepatopathy or sickle hepatopathy. Significant morbidity is caused by SCD due to the increasing impairment to multiple organs. Sickle cell disease patients have high velocities on transcranial Doppler, raised right-sided heart pressure, pulmonary hypertension, proteinuria, renal impairment, and an increased risk of stroke (particularly in youngsters). [78, 77] The natural history and pathophysiology of liver involvement in sickle cell disease (SCD) have not been thoroughly established. Consequently, a broad term known as sickle hepatopathy is used to describe all abnormalities resulting from the sickling process, including gallstone disease, hypoxic liver injury, hepatic sequestration, venous outflow obstruction, viral hepatitis (particularly in patients receiving multiple transfusions), hepatic crisis, and sickle cell intrahepatic cholestasis (SCIC). [79] Many writers would prefer to save this name for a more significant side effect that is currently known as intrahepatic cholestasis associated with sickle cell disease. [80] Up to one-third of patients will exhibit multiple pathophysiological abnormalities. While recurring bouts in some people might result in chronic and progressive liver failure, acute manifestations of SCIC are more common.

XIII- EPIDEMIOLOGY OF SICKLE CELL HEPATOPATHY

While liver impairment has been identified in approximately 10% of SCD patients, the total incidence of liver illness in these patients is not extensively documented.[81] Multiple blood transfusions, which result in viral hepatitis (hepatitis B and C), and high iron reserves are the main risk factors for liver disease development in these patients. About one-third of the patients may have abnormal liver function tests.[82] Numerous autopsy series have demonstrated that approximately 91% of SCD patients have hepatomegaly [83], while 16–29% of individuals have cirrhosis. It is likely that there are other contributing factors to cirrhosis, such as viral infections, iron overload, or even the illness itself.

XIV- HISTOLOGY OF THE LIVER IN SICKLE CELL DISEASE

The liver enzyme levels and symptoms may differ, but the biopsy specimens are strikingly identical and easily distinguished from other illnesses. All of them had sinusoidal dilatation, hyperplasia of Kupffer cells, and erythrophagocytosis. According to electron microscopy, the Disse gap is made up of more collagen in the basement membrane. The histology of the liver showed micronodular cirrhosis, portal fibrosis, and localised necrosis. Patients with SS and SC have the same liver pathology. SS patients' concluded causes of cirrhosis include:

- (a) Hypoxic injury froth sickling,
- (b) Hepatitis,
- (c) Gallstones,
- (d) Right heart failure,
- (e) Iron overloaded
- (f) Alcohol and other drugs.

XV- CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The treatment of sickle cell anaemia is one way that the traits of HbF are used medicinally. Because of its higher oxygen affinity, HbF appears to estimate between 2% and 20% of haemoglobin at baseline in sickle cell disease patients, depending on a variety of patient-dependent parameters. As a result, these patients are less likely to experience pain crises, deoxygenate, or

sickle from HbF. Indeed, because of their increased HbF, sickle cell disease patients do not exhibit symptoms during infancy; nevertheless, as HbF falls, symptoms do appear. Because hemolysis is caused by vaso-occlusive crises that arise during sickling and deoxygenation, haemoglobin A has a shorter half-life in sickle cell disease.

The pharmacologic medication hydroxyurea contributes to an increase in the proportion of HbF in adults through an unclear mechanism. Patients with acute chest syndrome, severe anaemia, or recurrent vaso-occlusive crises/pain crises may benefit from hydroxyurea treatment. Hydroxyurea reduces the need for blood transfusions in sickle cell disease patients by raising HbF. [15] the polymerization of sickle haemoglobin (HbS, $\alpha_2\beta_2$) caused by deoxygenation, which is responsible for the pathophysiology of sickle cell disease, can be inhibited by foetal haemoglobin (HbF). The drop in mean cell HbS concentration, which is a good measure of polymerization tendency, and the inability of HbF or its mixed hybrid tetramer to reach the deoxyHbS polymer phase account for this action of HbF. At one year of age, HbF typically decreases to 1% of total haemoglobin from 85% at birth, while adult haemoglobin (HbA) increases in the opposite direction.

XVI-HbF in SICKLE CELL DISEASE:

A- HAPLOTYPE OF THE β -GLOBIN OF THE GENE CLUSTER AND HbF

Sickle cell disease and HbF Haplotypes of HbF and the β -globin gene cluster. There are four main haplotypes that have the b-globin gene cluster associated with sickle cell anaemia: Bantu, Benin, Senegal, and Arab-Indian (AI). These haplotypes differ in mean HbF concentrations. Each haplotype group exhibits a wide range of HbF concentrations, indicating that factors associated with the b-globin gene cluster are not the primary drivers of the variability observed in HbF concentration and F-cell counts. The β -globin gene cluster's AI and Senegal haplotypes are linked to the greatest HbF levels, and those who carry them may have milder forms of the disease. However, they are frequently symptomatic and anaemic.

B- HbS AND HERIDITARY PERSISTENCE OF HbF

HbF's inherited persistence and HbS Patients with compound heterozygosity for HbS and gene deletion hereditary persistence of HbF (HPFH) typically have a HbF level of 30% and neither sickle cell disease nor hemolytic anaemia symptoms. All of the erythrocytes in HbS-HPFH are dispersed with HbF, meaning that each cell should have 10 pg of HbF when the mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration is normal. Research indicates that when HbF/F-cell is 9 to 12 pg, deoxyHbS polymerization is inhibited at physiological venous and capillary O₂ saturations of 40% to 70% [64]. Neither experimentally nor after determining the HbS polymer fraction at 70% O₂ saturation does HbS polymer exist in the erythrocytes of HbS-HPFH.[14] In sickle cell anaemia, HbS polymer is present at 70% O₂ saturation, and the polymer percentage grows sharply with decreasing O₂ saturation. These results suggest that, in comparison to the total number of F-cells or the concentration of HbF in the hemolysate, the number of F-cells with polymer-inhibiting amounts of HbF is a more important determinant of the features of sickle cell anaemia.

C- HbF AND CLINICAL COMPLICATIONS

When compared to African American patients and Saudi Arabs with the Benin haplotype, adult sickle cell anaemia patients with the AI haplotype had HbF levels almost four times higher. Adults with the AI haplotype had almost the same frequency of painful episodes, acute chest syndrome, and osteonecrosis even with a HbF of 15% to 20% as did African Americans and Saudi Arabs with the Benin haplotype. Though not as severe as in sickle cell anaemia, they nonetheless experience

anaemia and vaso-occlusive consequences. HbF ranges of some African Americans with sickle cell disease are comparable to those of people with the AI haplotype.[88] Their illness is not benign, similar to adult patients with AI haplotypes. HbF is irregularly distributed among erythrocytes in all of these patient groups, in contrast to HbS-HPFH.

D- HbF AND HYDROXYUREA

Hydroxyurea and HbF together reduce sickle cell anemia's morbidity and death; this effect is mostly, though not entirely, due to the induction of HbF. The HbF response to hydroxyurea varies; among patients who respond to therapy, some reach very high HbF levels and others do not. Some patients do not respond to therapy at all. Hydroxyurea does not treat sickle cell anaemia as a result. Patients who get hydroxyurea therapy live longer and are in better health, although they are rarely asymptomatic, particularly when hydroxyurea is started in adults after HbF levels have stabilized. When hydroxyurea medication is used to successfully induce high levels, HbF is distributed heterocellularly.

E- HbF AS A PREDICTOR OF PHENOTYPES

Patients with sickle cell disease who had HbF 8.6% had a higher survival rate than those whose HbF levels were lower. These findings are consistent with our calculations, in which 65 indicate that at HbF levels of 5%, there are very few protected F-cells, but above 10%, there may be more protected cells. Due to the extremely varied distribution of HbF among F-cells, HbF concentration for a given patient is not very predictive. Higher HbF levels were associated with a lower incidence of acute painful episodes, fewer leg ulcers, a lower incidence of osteonecrosis, fewer acute chest syndromes, and a lower severity of disease in cross-sectional investigations. Furthermore, there was either no discernible correlation or a weak one between the HbF level and tricuspid regurgitant velocity, urine albumin excretion, stroke and silent cerebral infarction, and priapism. Heme products, which scavenge nitric oxide and enable the development of endothelial damage and other consequences of diminished nitric oxide bioavailability, are released into the circulation during erythrocyte lysis. It is also plausible that the pathophysiology of some hemolysis-related issues depends more on blood flow, oxidative damage, or inflammation—essential mediators of disease pathobiology—and is less dependent on HbS polymerization, making it less likely to be altered by HbF.

XVII- THERAPEUTIC IMPLICATIONS

Since it targets the disease's proximal pathophysiologic trigger, inducing large levels of HbF is the most promising pharmacologic therapeutic option for sickle cell anaemia. Hydroxyurea is clinically effective in many cases and can decrease HbF in the majority of patients. Nonetheless, hydroxyurea-responding patients with haemoglobin levels close to 20% may experience abrupt, potentially fatal consequences. Following therapy commencement shortly after birth, the majority of individuals experience hemolytic problems and persistent, albeit diminished, Vaso occlusive episodes. Early treatment seems to slow down the decline in HbF, but the sneaky decline after age 10 suggests that these individuals may also experience worsening symptoms because, even at 20% HbF, many F-cells will be inadequately protected against polymer-induced damage. The hunt for alternative HbF induction treatments has been sparked by this. An essential suppressor of the expression of the γ -globin gene is BCL11A. In transgenic sickle mice, its inactivation results in the problems associated with sickle cell disease. These animals exhibited pan-cellular HbF spread in their erythrocytes, which is comparable to what is observed in HbS-HPFH. [89] It is unknown if

inhibiting BCL11A or its route in people will cause HbF to diffuse heterocellularly or pancellularly among erythrocytes. Most illness complications should be treated pharmacologically if the dissemination in HbS-HPFH is pancellular-like and total HbF levels of 30% can be reached. When combined with an agent whose main mechanism of action is to increase the transcription of the γ -globin genes, combination treatment with medications that affect the kinetics of erythropoiesis and potentially widen the distribution of F-cells may be the most productive approach to HbF induction therapy, outperforming single agent treatment in cases where the dissemination is heterocellular, such as in patients receiving hydroxyurea.

XVIII- COMPLICATIONS OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE:

A- ACENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

Cerebral vasculopathy, the most prevalent cause of CNS intricacies in children, results from oxidative endothelial damage and progressive inflammation inside intracranial arteries, increasing the likelihood of transient ischemia episodes and infarctive strokes. The severity of long-term consequences might range from minor behavioural or cognitive impairment to fatal neurological consequences. It is advised to begin screening for vasculopathy at the age of two and to start disease-modifying medication early in order to reduce endothelial damage and anaemia. Acute cranial bone infarction, which is linked to cerebral haemorrhage and/or thrombosis, is another uncommon condition that can manifest with acute neurologic symptoms. It is thought that diploic vascular disruption brought on by extramedullary hemopoiesis causes cerebral bone infarcts. [90]

B- CARDIOVASCULAR COMPLICATIONS

Many children who have mild to moderate left ventricular hypertrophy and hyperdynamic blood flow may present with clinical murmurs as a symptom of cardiovascular complications. It may take until maturity for pulmonary hypertension and cardiomyopathy brought on by iron overload to show clinical symptoms. Children should not usually have screening echocardiograms unless they exhibit new symptoms or clinical findings during an evaluation. [91]

C- PULMONARY HYPERTENSION

Studies have suggested that individuals with sickle cell anaemia frequently experience pulmonary hypertension (PHTN). According to a prospective study on sickle cell anaemia, children 10 years of age and older had a 31% prevalence of pulmonary hypertension. Prostanoids like epoprostenol (Flolan, GlaxoSmithKline) and phosphodiesterase-5 inhibitors like sildenafil citrate (Revatio, Pfizer) are being used to treat conventional PHTN with increasing evidence. In 2005, the FDA approved sildenafil for the management of PHTN. Eight PHTN patients underwent cardiac catheterization as part of a study conducted at the Howard University Centre for Sickle Cell Disease to investigate the reversibility of PHTN. Prostacyclin infusions were given to the patients. [92]

D- APLASTIC CRISIS

An erythrotropic virus called Aplastic Crisis Parvovirus –B19 targets human red blood cells and their progenitors specifically. Because of the abrupt stop of erythropoiesis, this can result in potentially fatal anaemia in sickle cell disease patients. When there is no blood loss or sequestration, the clinical indications of anaemia include an abrupt decrease in haemoglobin and reticulocytopenia. It is advised to receive a blood transfusion and receive attention right away to avoid heart collapse and death.

E- SPLENIC COMPLICATIONS

Children with splenic problems may have weakened immune systems to encapsulated pathogens including *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Neisseria meningitidis*, and *Salmonella* species, making them more vulnerable to potentially fatal infections like pneumonia, meningitis, osteomyelitis, and sepsis. Therefore, until shown differently in infants and toddlers with compromised immune systems, all feverish infections are considered medical emergencies. Primary care physicians deliver the recommended childhood vaccinations, along with the extended pneumococcal and meningococcal vaccines as part of normal care. Early infancy vaccination with prophylactic antibiotics has greatly decreased the morbidity and death that were previously linked to these diseases. Another potentially serious consequence in paediatric patients is acute splenic sequestration of red blood cells and/or platelets. Since auto splenectomy has been reported to be less likely in children who begin disease-modifying medication early in life, older children and teenagers may experience this consequence. Predictive advice for parents must include a review of splenic palpation and anaemia symptoms, as well as the necessity of an immediate red cell transfusion if circulatory failure symptoms continue.

F- GASTROINTESTINAL COMPLICATIONS

Acute abdominal discomfort may manifest as a vascular blockage in intra-abdominal vessels. In some patients, a thorough assessment for potential secondary causes of acute abdomen may yield no information. Pain management and hydration are the appropriate treatments for these vaso-occlusive events. A spectrum of hepatic consequences, ranging from minor liver dysfunction to chronic liver failure and cirrhosis, are associated with sickle hepatopathy. Similar to the acute abdominal presentation above, fever, jaundice, transaminitis, and severe abdominal pain might be symptoms of acute vaso-occlusive disorders within the hepatic parenchyma. [93]

G- GENITOURINARY COMPLICATIONS:

Sickle nephropathy is a condition in which the renal medullary vasculature experiences hypoxia and ischemia, leading to micro-infarction and papillary necrosis. Furthermore, free haemoglobin produced by intravascular hemolysis may cause oxidative injury to renal tubular cells. Nephropathy can manifest itself in a variety of ways, ranging from proteinuria and microalbuminuria to severe renal failure and dysfunction. Individuals with severe hemolysis and anaemia are more vulnerable. Microalbuminuria can be detected annually, beginning at age 10, as an early indicator of nephropathy. It has been demonstrated that using ACE inhibitors in addition to SCD-modifying medication slows the evolution of nephropathy. Pruritus in male patients refers to an undesired, painful, and prolonged erection that can occur at any age. As a first resort, conservative methods like exercise, diversion, or warm baths are advised to reroute penile blood flow. A α -adrenergic agonist that can be administered as needed at home for sporadic episodes is pseudoephedrine. More than four hours of painful episodes are deemed urologic emergencies. [94]

XIX- RARE COMPLICATIONS OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

Small infarcts of the mesentery and abdominal viscera are the cause of the abdominal crisis, which manifests as acute abdominal pain, peritoneal irritation, and a plain film that frequently displays a generalised ileus. It's possible that the clinical picture is identical to other acute abdominal illnesses. In the absence of other causes, acute pancreatitis may arise from ischemia damage and microvascular blockage. Acute chest syndrome or the pancreatitis itself may produce

pulmonary symptoms in patients with acute pancreatitis. Thirty-five percent of patients with SCD who also have epigastric pain have peptic ulcer disease. Remarkably, increased acid output does not cause duodenal ulcers. This suggests that decreased mucosal resistance, potentially brought on by ischemia, may be the true cause of these ulcers. Ischemic bowel is a rare consequence that arises from intravascular sickling and microvascular blockage.

A shock equivalent that results in ischemia necrosis and vascular spasm may be seen in sickle cell crisis. According to one report, there was hypotension and deadly small bowel necrosis. Because of the substantial collateral circulation in the mesentery and intestinal wall, ischemic bowel is rare in patients with sickle cell disease (SCD). Due to its circumferential distribution, abdominal pain with a suspected vaso-occlusive origin—often referred to as "girdle syndrome"—rarely manifests as ischemic colitis. Exchange transfusions have been used to treat pseudo membranous colitis without *Clostridium difficile* in patients with sickle cell disease (SCD). Unusual hydrogen breath tests may indicate dysmotile gastrointestinal tract or aberrant gut microbiota.

FIGURE 9: COMPLICATIONS OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE [96]

XX- DIAGNOSIS OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

Patients with sickle cell disease may exhibit varying degrees of hepatic involvement, ranging from mild jaundice to potentially fatal illnesses such as acute liver failure (ALF) or acute on chronic liver failure (ACLF). A sickle cell disease patient should have a thorough examination if there is a suspicion of liver abnormalities; bear in mind that one-third of sickle cell disease patients may have unrelated comorbidities. Consequently, in these individuals, frequent causes of hepatic illness in India, such as drug-induced liver injury and viral hepatitis, must always be ruled out. A thorough clinical assessment should be conducted regarding medications, alcohol, and the existence of metabolic syndrome. Regular abdominal ultrasound exams should include the evaluation of the biliary system and vascular patency. When necessary, additional imaging modalities such as magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), CT abdomen, and endoscopic ultrasound should also be used. Hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV), HIV, CMV, Epstein-Barr virus, hepatitis A virus (HAV), and hepatitis E virus (HEV) should all be tested for in sickle cell disease patients.

Investigations into antinuclear antibody, smooth muscle, liver/kidney antibody, anti-soluble liver antigen, antimitochondrial antibody, alpha-fetoprotein levels, and ceruloplasmin/Wilson

screening should also be conducted in sickle cell disease cases that are included. In certain circumstances, vital tests such as an MRI to measure liver iron concentration, serum ferritin, and iron status assessment will also be necessary. It is important to thoroughly rule out other possible causes before considering the diagnosis of debarring sickle cell disease-related hepatic damage. Individuals who exhibit substantial involvement of the liver may show signs of encephalopathy and coagulopathy. To determine whether these patients require a liver transplant, coagulation markers such as prothrombin time (PT) and the international normalised ratio (INR) should be carefully monitored in addition to liver and renal functions.

Diseases that can mimic sickle cell disease in the Indian subcontinent include leptospirosis, malaria, and scrub typhus; for this reason, they should be avoided. In a same vein, acute presentations such as sickle hepatic crisis are uncommon in autoimmune hepatitis (AIH) and Wilson's disease (WD). Consequently, screening for Wilson's disease and autoimmune hepatitis should be done on all patients whose sickle cell illness presents as an acute hepatic crisis. In order to determine if these critically ill patients need an exchange transfusion and to monitor their response to treatment, haemoglobin electrophoresis should also be carried out on a frequent basis. The risk-benefit ratio needs to be carefully considered in order to determine the liver histology. It should only be carried out if the outcomes are anticipated to alter how sickle cell disease patients are treated. a transjugular liver biopsy was carried out.

XXI- ADVANCES IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

Sickle cell disease diagnosis is typically straightforward and is not often regarded as a significant obstacle. Even though the disease's named sickle-shaped red blood cell isn't always present in the patient's blood film, an electrophoretic analysis of HbS's distinctive migration can accurately diagnose sickling disorders. For some sickling genotypes, electrophoresis provides a conclusive diagnosis, but not for others. An indication of HbS β -thalassemia, for instance, is when a sickle cell disease patient has less Hb A in their blood than Hb S. Furthermore, when no Hb A is detected by electrophoresis, it can be considerably more challenging to distinguish between homozygous HbSS and HbS β 0-thalassemia. In these cases, a low mean corpuscular volume and an elevated Hb A2 level are used to diagnose HbS β 0-thalassemia. Fortunately, every patient with a haemoglobin disease can receive a definitive molecular diagnosis at one of the many top reference laboratories in the United States.

The main difficulty in diagnosing sickling disorders is identifying the condition during the prenatal stage, when such information would be vitally important to help a couple at risk decide whether to terminate their current pregnancy or not. It is important to consider the significant variations in the expected clinical severity of the various sickling illnesses covered above when making such selections. The sole method of diagnosing a foetus before to the discovery of molecular diagnostics was to obtain a sample of foetal blood for analysis, which could only be done after the 20th week of pregnancy. By then, the pregnancy has progressed too far to allow for a safe termination. With the advancement of DNA diagnostics, it is now feasible to examine foetal DNA collected by chorionic villous biopsy in order to make firm diagnoses of the many sickling syndromes during the first trimester. More advancement are being made in molecular diagnostic technology, which will enable the diagnosis to be made from the few foetal cells that can be removed from the mother's blood.

XXII- APPROPRIATE TECHNOLOGIES FOR SCREENING

The sickling or solubility test was used in the majority of the early studies based on the epidemiology of sickle cell haemoglobin in various parts of the nation. In many reports, this was

followed by Hb electrophoresis, which is done to determine the phenotypes in sickle cell disease patients and subsequently confirms the disease. Nonetheless, in recent times, numerous extensive initiatives have integrated high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) testing to detect sickle haemoglobin and β -thalassaemia carriers. In certain centers, capillary electrophoresis is now also utilized. But even the easy and affordable solubility test can still serve as a good first line screening for sickle haemoglobin in remote areas without access to other facilities, as it has been shown to have a sensitivity and specificity of 97.4 and 100%, respectively, when compared to HPLC. [98]

XXIII- MANAGEMENT OF SICKLE CELL DISEASE

A- INDUCTION OF Hb F

The idea that administering Hb F can lessen the clinical severity of SCD is supported by a substantial body of epidemiological, clinical, and laboratory data. 74 Individuals with sickle cell disease from India and the eastern provinces of Saudi Arabia usually have a relatively mild sickling illness linked to elevated Hb F levels.

B- 5-AZACYTIDINE

5-Azacytidine was the first medication to be used to epigenetically silence the γ -globin genes in adulthood in order to stimulate Hb F expression. The finding that the non-transcribed foetal γ -globin genes are hypermethylated in adulthood and the actively transcribed adult β -globin genes are hypomethylated provided the justification for this strategy. On the other hand, the γ -globin genes are hypomethylated in foetal life and hypermethylated in adult β -globin genes. In anaemic baboons, azacytidine was demonstrated to cause extremely high levels of Hb F. Its capacity to promote the synthesis of Hb F was also shown in a small subset of β -thalassemia and SCD patients. [99]

C- HYDROXYUREA

With its several modes of action, hydroxyurea offers therapeutic benefit in sickle cell anaemia (SCA) and possesses many of the qualities of a perfect medication. Considerable experience has been gained over the previous 25 years with relation to its effectiveness and safety for sickle cell anaemia patients. In critically ill individuals, the phase 3 National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute-subsidized multicenter hydroxyurea trial demonstrated clinical efficacy in preventing acute vaso-occlusive events. Hydroxyurea has become a major treatment strategy for children and adolescents with recurrent vaso occlusive episodes based on this progressive experience; recent confirmation shows sustained long-term benefits with prevention or modification of chronic organ damage.

Nevertheless, hydroxyurea has not yet resulted in an effective treatment for sickle cell anaemia, despite a wealth of evidence supporting its effectiveness. Many medical professionals lack sufficient understanding regarding the hydroxyurea medication; as a result, patients and their families either do not receive treatment or decline due to unfounded fear. The underutilization of hydroxyurea was partly caused by uneven medical delivery systems and limited support for the medication from lay organizations. Current research suggests that many young sickle cell disease patients should get hydroxyurea treatment, even if there are still uncertainties about the drug's long-term dangers and benefits. "The risks of hydroxyurea are embracing compared with the risks of untreated sickle cell disease," the panel of the National Institutes of Health Consensus Conference stated in their examination of the negative consequences of hydroxyurea treatment. [100]

XXIV- INDICATIONS IN SICKLE CELL ANAEMIA [101]

STANDARD INDICATIONS (any of the following)

1. Frequent vaso-occlusive crises/pain crises.
2. Suffering from acute chest syndrome.
3. Fatal or symptomatic anemia (Hb $\leq$ 7 g/dL).
4. Associated with Haemolytic alloantibodies/autoantibodies.
5. Severe intrications without benefit from standard therapy (priapism, leg ulceration).

SCENARIOS TO BE INCLUDED (not proven effective)

1. Chronic blood transfusion therapy is prohibited if there are several allo-antibodies present.
2. An abnormal cerebral doppler that declines blood transfusion treatment.
3. A history of stroke refusal or patients who refuse to comply with chelation or transfusion therapy.

A- DOCUMENTATION

DRUG ADMINISTRATION:

- i. Document informed consent with patient and/or parent/ guardian of minor patients. It should contain discussion of required monitoring, potential toxicity, potential teratogenicity/carcinogenicity and requirement for contraception/abstinence.
- ii. Signed and written consent is not required as hydroxyurea is FDA approved in adults with sickle cell disease and Phase II safety studies have been performed on children.
- iii. Additional information should be provided to parents of younger children, availability of data on their age group and potential concerns.

B- DOSING

1. Initial dose 10–15 mg/kg/day given as a single daily dose.
2. Dose escalation by 5 mg/kg every 4–6 weeks.
3. Increase dose until one of the following:
4. Evidence of hematological toxicity (see below) and thus “maximal tolerated dose” (MTD)
5. Goal ANC 2000–3000 achieved • 35 mg/kg/day dose achieved.
6. If clear positive clinical and/or hematological effect is observed before MTD can consider stopping escalation, although there is some evidence of dose response that would suggest continuing to MTD may enhance clinical effect further.
7. Re-evaluation of dosage (mg/kg) will occur with each monitoring visit.
8. How supplied: 500 mg capsules.
9. Liquid formulation can be prepared by compounding pharmacy using published guideline. Alternatively, capsules may be opened and dissolved into a glass of water with vigorous stirring.

10. Laboratory evaluation every 2–4 weeks:
11. CBC, differential, reticulocyte count.
12. Bilirubin, ALT, BUN, Cr every dose escalation.
13. Inquiry regarding side-effects, sexual activity and birth control.

C- MONITORING VISITS

1, DOSE ESCALATION

1. Clinical examination visits every 4 weeks (more frequently if education or compliance needs reinforcement).
2. Weight, BP, vital signs and pulse SaO₂.
3. Hematological system and toxicity focused physical exam each visit.
4. Quantitative HbF Q 3–6 months.
5. Record all lab values and evidence of toxicity and side effects on flow sheet. A brief clinical note to be completed for each visit.
6. Continue until patient has been at stable or maximal tolerated dose for 8 weeks without toxicity.
7. Clinical and laboratory examination visits every 4–8 weeks.
8. CBC with differential and reticulocyte count every 4–8 weeks.
9. Quantitative HbF every 6–12 months.
10. ALT, AST, BUN, Cr every 6 months.
11. Weight, BP, vital signs and pulse SaO₂.
12. Hematological system and toxicity focused physical exam each visit.
13. Inquiry regarding side-effects, sexual activity and birth control.

XXV- ANTIADHESIVE THERAPIES

A- INTRAVENOUS IMMUNOGLOBULIN

Intravenous immunoglobulin increased survival and microcirculatory blood flow in a sickle cell animal model by blocking the contacts between neutrophil endothelium adhesive and RBC-neutrophil. [108] In order to assess the safety and effectiveness of intravenous immunoglobulin in SCD patients experiencing a pain crisis within 24 hours of admission, a phase 2 trial is presently accepting participants (HbSS and HbS b-thalassemia, NCT01757418).

B- HEPARIN

Heparins have anti-inflammatory properties and prevent adhesion mediated by P-selectin. Tinzaparin, a low-molecular-weight heparin, was found to shorten the length of vaso-occlusive

crisis in a randomised, double-blind experiment without causing any serious bleeding problems. To evaluate the impact of unfractionated heparin in acute chest syndrome, a feasibility trial is presently accepting subjects (NCT02098993).

C- PROPRANOLOL

Propranolol reduced sickle RBC adherence in a dose-dependent way when human RBCs from individuals were treated with propranolol and homozygous sickle cell disease were injected into naked mice in a phase 1 dose-escalation trial. At 40 mg, maximum inhibition was reached. There were no notable variations in heart rate or serious side effects noted. In patients with homozygous sickle cell disease treated with propranolol compared with placebo, levels of measured soluble biomarkers such as E-selectin, P-selectin, intercellular adhesion molecule 1, and vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 were found to be lower in the double-blind crossover phase 2 study; however, these decreases were not statistically significant.[109]

XXVI- ANTIPLATELET THERAPY

Patients with sickle cell disease are more likely to have activated platelets, which can cause vaso-occlusion through their involvement in intercellular adhesion and formation of multicellular aggregates.

A- PRASUGREL

It is a third-generation thienopyridine that binds irreversibly to the P2Y₁₂ family of adenosine diphosphate receptors to prevent adenosine diphosphate-mediated platelet activation and to cause aggregation. A phase 3, double-blind, placebo-controlled study of prasugrel in children and adolescents with homozygous HbSS aged 2 to 17 years was conducted to determine the effects of platelet inhibition on vaso-occlusive events (DOVE trial). The study found no evidence of a decreased rate of vaso-occlusive crises with prasugrel therapy.[110] Another antiplatelet medication, Eptifibatide, a platelet glycoprotein aIIb β 3 antagonist, inhibited platelet aggregation and supported modified inflammatory mediators in a phase 1 trial of sickle cell anaemia patients.

In 13 SCD patients experiencing acute pain crises, a phase 2 placebo-controlled trial revealed the safety of eptifibatide; however, no improvement in recovery periods or time to hospital discharge was observed. According to a secondary investigation, eptifibatide reduced platelet-leukocyte aggregation and inflammatory indicators while also inhibiting platelet aggregation, release, and P-selectin expression. The lack of benefit from antiplatelet drug monotherapy in sickle cell disease patients raises the possibility that alternative vaso-occlusive processes are more clearly involved in the pathophysiology of the disease. Nevertheless, more investigation using high-powered studies is necessary to conclusively determine if antiplatelet medications are effective in treating or preventing pain.

XXVII- TREATMENT OF ANEMIA

Many SCD patients may away in hospital wards and emergency rooms before blood transfusions can be administered since anaemia is a major cause of morbidity and death in the disease. Results of a 2007 study by Ikefuna and Emodi, which involved 71 children hospitalised in Nigeria for sickle cell disease.[112] Results showed that 39.4% of individuals had severe anaemia, and the majority of these instances were linked to acute sequestration, hyper-haemolytic, vasculo-occlusive, and aplastic crises. Nonetheless, the authors argued that it was critical to check for additional causes of anaemia in SCD patients, such as septicemia and malaria parasitemia. Blood

transfusions are commonly administered in patients with sickle cell disease (SCD) either as a long-term therapy to prevent stroke or as an interim intervention to correct hypovolemia or anaemia, as Stewart and Nagel first reported in 2004. [113]

Following are indications for transfusion therapy:

1. chronic splenic sequestration
2. severe or lasting aplastic crises
3. acute stroke
4. acute chest syndrome; and
5. Haemolytic episodes associated with malaria.

A- Indications for chronic transfusions are:

1. Stroke prevention and
2. Chronic pulmonary hypertension. [160]

Chelation treatment may be used to prevent iron excess brought on by ongoing transfusions. Makani noted in 2007 that there is a shortage of blood in Sub-Saharan Africa, which limits the availability of blood and increases the risk of HIV transmission due to inadequate blood screening. Reference 114 the sergeant warned that in many African settings, a lack of human and diagnostic resources would prevent an adequate examination into the cause of anaemia and the utilisation of blood transfusions.

XXVIII-CURATIVE MODALITIES:

A- BONE MARROW TRANSPLANT

In a sickle cell patient, a bone marrow transplant (BMT) replaces the malfunctioning "machinery" that creates aberrant sickle red blood cells (RBCs) with a functional marrow that produces normal, non-sickle RBCs. It was pure serendipity that the first successful bone marrow transplant to treat sickle cell disease occurred. A young paediatric kid was treated for both leukaemia and sickle cell disease through a transplant procedure, which also led to the patient's leukaemia being cured. [115]

B- GENE THERAPY

Gene therapy is still in its early stages, but it holds promise for a treatment for sickle cell disease. In order to introduce a therapeutic anti-sickling coding gene (gene addition), induce Hb F by silencing gamma globin gene repressors (HbF induction), or correct sickle gene mutations using genomic engineering techniques like Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats (CRISPR)/Cas9 (gene correction), viral vectors are used.[116]

In 2017, the first effective gene treatment for sickle cell disease was reported. This involved inserting an anti-sickling beta-globin gene into the patient's hematopoietic stem cells using a lentiviral vector. Currently, numerous clinical trials are making progress in determining the effectiveness of gene therapy for individuals with sickle cell disease. There are no conclusive anecdotal accounts of successful gene therapy. But, care must be taken because, as with all comprehensive clinical research, continuous trials must be started in order to determine the effectiveness of the intervention.

XXIX- INVESTIGATIONAL TREATMENT OPTIONS

A- NIPRISAN

The National Institute for Pharmaceutical Research and Development in Nigeria produced Niprisan, a phytopharmaceutical derived from a plant in its natural state. Developed by Xechem International, this anti-sickling chemical was given orphan medication classification by the FDA in 2003. Because of its capacity to prolong or postpone the time to polymerization of deoxy-Hb S, it is thought to possess anti-sickling properties. According to a phase 2, double-blind, placebo-controlled, six-month randomised crossover trial; the Niprisan arm experienced a substantial reduction in sickle cell pain crisis recurrence. [117]

B- NITRIC OXIDE

Nitric oxide (NO) has been promoted as a treatment option since it is a strong vasodilator that is thought to be lacking in sickle cell disease patients. The method of action involves preventing red blood cells from adhering to blood channel walls or expanding peripheral blood vessels, hence preventing sickling of RBCs. Research conducted by Head and colleagues revealed that either in vitro when red blood cells are exposed to nitric oxide or in vivo when extremely low amounts of nitric oxide are inhaled, the haemoglobin oxygen propinquity in homozygous HbS (SS) erythrocytes is elevated by NO. [118] Although research suggests that NO modifies HbS, decreasing polymerization and increasing oxygen propinquity in sickled red blood cells, it is still unclear how low concentrations of nitric oxide regulate oxygen propinquity of erythrocytes in sickle cell disease when compared with normal erythrocytes.

C- L-ARGININE

For endothelial cells, platelets, and other cells to synthesise nitric acid, they require the amino acid L-arginine as a demanding substrate. Adults with sickle cell disease began with markedly reduced arginine levels when there was a NO shortage. In sickle cell patients, arginine deficiency may result in pulmonary hypertension. Consequently, it has been determined that giving L-arginine to newborns with pulmonary hypertension lowers vascular resistance and improves blood oxygenation. Within one week of starting treatment, an earlier study found that supplementing with L-arginine improved both the haemodynamic and pulmonary artery pressures in patients with main and secondary hypertension. All things considered, arginine was well tolerated with few side effects. [119]

D- L-GLUTAMINE

Patients with sickle cell anaemia are deficient in nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD), which is thought to be a precursor of glutamine. Immunosuppression, poor wound healing, and skeletal muscular atrophy can result from a glutamine shortage. It is suggested that the rate at which glutamate, a byproduct of glutamine, is actively transported in sickled red blood cells is the cause of the glutamine shortage. Because oral L-glutamine therapy increases NAD synthesis activity, it can benefit patients with sickle cell anaemia by preventing the oxidant-dependent pathophysiology of sickled red blood cells. Niihara and colleagues reported that seven sickle cell anaemia patients, ranging in age from 19 to 60, showed a significant increase in NAD redox potential (the ratio of NADH to NAD⁺ plus NADH) and NADH (the reduced form of NAD) after receiving 30 g of oral L-glutamine for four weeks. Additionally, there was an overall improvement in these participants' energy levels, which was correlated with higher activity levels and lower levels of chronic pain. All

things considered, the oral delivery of L-glutamine has demonstrated a steady and noteworthy rise in red blood cell NADH and has been well tolerated by the patients with no negative side effects.[120]

E- MAGNESIUM

According to De Franceschi *et al.*, preventing erythrocyte dehydration could lower the cellular concentration of sickle cell haemoglobin (HbS), which could be a potential therapeutic strategy for sickle cell disease (SCD).[121] The potassium chloride transporter, which is blocked after raising the erythrocyte magnesium level, is the primary determinant of sickle cell dehydration. Oral magnesium supplementation has been shown to significantly raise the content of magnesium and potassium in sickle erythrocytes while decreasing the quantity of dense sickle erythrocytes. The authors began by stating that ingesting magnesium reduces the amount of dense erythrocytes and improves sickle cell patients' aberrant erythrocyte membrane transport, both of which lessen erythrocyte dehydration.

XXX- MORBIDITY IN SICKLE CELL DISEASE

Many different body organs experience difficulties as a result of the sickle cell disease. The following are some of the most prevalent morbidities linked to sickle cell disease:

1. Chronic pain and intermittent painful episodes,
2. Musculoskeletal problems,
3. Stroke,
4. Pulmonary hypertension, and

XXXI- MORTALITY RATES IN SICKLE CELL DISEASE

Worldwide, the mortality rates related to sickle cell disease are not constant. When it comes to major hemoglobinopathies (like SCD), children born in high-income nations have a better chance of surviving and a lower death rate than children born in developing nations.[125] Patients with sickle cell disease may live longer in affluent nations due to early diagnosis, easier access to care, carer education, and improved disease management. In the United States (U.S.), patients with sickle cell disease can expect to live for 42 years for men and 48 years for women. Quinn *et al.* (2010) found that among children with sickle cell disease who were followed up in Dallas, Texas, 93.9% of them survived to adulthood (Quinn, Rogers, McCavit, & Buchanan, 2010).[126] The life expectancy in Jamaica is 58.5 years for women and 53 years for males (Wierenga, Hambleton, & Lewis, 2001).[127] On the other hand, statistics from 2010 by Aygun and Odame state that 50–80% of African children born with sickle cell illness pass away before turning five. Several reasons contribute to Sub-Saharan Africa's high death rates, such as a lack of comprehensive sickle cell disease management programmes and scarce resources that impede access to care. Most poor resource countries are unable to implement interventions like newborn screening and prophylactic penicillin injection, which have been shown to be successful in reducing mortality among sickle cell disease patients in wealthier nations.

XXXII- CHALLENGES AND PITFALLS

The limited clinical arsenal against sickle cell disease is a result of tiny clinical studies and unequal financing from the National Institutes of Health. However, research is currently being conducted to identify new treatments for sickle cell disease. Due to the requirement for age- and genotype-specific research, the current evidence for many therapies are insufficient. Many clinical concerns and challenges remain unresolved, which limits the therapy of sickle cell disease such as Three main issues need to be addressed: (1) treatment options for pregnant sickle cell disease patients; (2) the moral quandaries surrounding the current state of hematopoietic stem cell transplantation and gene therapy, particularly for asymptomatic patients; and (3) the best way to manage pain for a population that experiences acute and chronic pain episodes throughout their lives, which worsen with age and change with socioeconomic stressors. [128]

XXXIII-CURRENT AND FUTURE THERAPIES TARGETING SICKLE CELL DISEASE PATHOBIOLGY

Many present and possible future therapeutic treatments to avoid sickle cell disease morbidity have been inspired by our growing understanding of the cellular, molecular, and biophysical pathobiology of sickle cell disease. These treatments enhance the severity of the disease by addressing several aspects of the pathobiology of sickle cell disease. Certain related or prospective interventions can prevent HbS polymerization and preserve erythrocyte deformability by stimulating the production of HbF (hydroxyurea, metformin, and sodium butyrate), altering HbS oxygen affinity allosterically (5-hydroxymethyl-2-furfural or Aes-103), preventing erythrocyte dehydration (senicapoc), or acting as carbon monoxide (CO) donors (PEGylated bovine carboxyhaemoglobin).

Apart from interventions like as antipolymerization or antisickling, there are various antiadhesion therapies that are linked to the inhibition of the multicellular adhesion cascade in vaso-occlusion. Targeted therapies aimed at preventing erythrocyte adhesion are focused towards several targets, such as P-selectin (crizanlizumab), E-selectin (rivipansel), Mac-1 (intravenous immunoglobulin), platelet glycoprotein Iba (CCP-224), or mitogen-activated protein kinase inhibitors (MEK inhibitors). By scavenging cell-free Hb (haptoglobin), increasing NO synthesis (hydroxyurea, oral or IV nitrite, inhaled NO, and oral arginine), or reducing oxidative stress (L-glutamine and antioxidants), additional recommended or FDA-approved therapies may prevent endothelial dysfunction. Anti-inflammatory interventions, such as those that induce the heme degradation enzyme hemoxygenase-1 (MP4CO), scavenge ROS (antioxidants and L-glutamine), inhibit TLR4 signalling, degrade NETs (DNase-1), inhibit leukotrienes, or inhibit inflammasome- or IL-1 β -dependent signalling, may be beneficial in sickle cell disease patients, as suggested by the emerging role of sterile inflammation in sickle cell disease-associated morbidity. The available data supports the necessity of conducting clinical trials to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of repurposing these medications in patients with sickle cell illness. It also indicates that additional research is required to further our understanding of the function of inflammasome pathways in sickle cell disease.

Sickle cell hepatopathy, also known as sickle hepatopathy, refers to a range of liver diseases that can result from a wide range of liver injuries in sickle cell disease patients. Because sickle cell disease damages multiple organs gradually, it significantly increases morbidity. Sickle cell disease patients have high velocities on transcranial Doppler, raised right-sided heart pressure, pulmonary hypertension, proteinuria, renal impairment, and an increased risk of stroke (particularly in youngsters). In terms of its natural history and pathophysiology, as well as all the abnormalities that arise from the sickling process, such as gallstone disease, hypoxic liver injury, hepatic sequestration, venous outflow obstruction, viral hepatitis (particularly in patients receiving multiple

transfusions), hepatic crisis, and sickle cell intrahepatic cholestasis, liver involvement in sickle cell disease has not been well-proven. Many writers would prefer to save this name for a more significant side effect that is currently known as intrahepatic cholestasis associated with sickle cell disease. Up to one-third of patients will exhibit multiple pathophysiological abnormalities. [129] while recurring bouts in some people might result in chronic and progressive liver failure, acute manifestations of SCIC are more common.

XXXIV-CONCLUSION

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) remains a complex genetic disorder that affects millions worldwide, particularly those of African, Mediterranean, Middle Eastern, and Indian descent. The disease causes significant morbidity and mortality due to its effects on red blood cells, leading to chronic pain, organ damage, and a reduced lifespan for affected individuals.

Despite these challenges, advancements in medical research and treatment have improved outcomes for many with SCD. Treatments such as hydroxyurea, blood transfusions, and potentially curative options like bone marrow transplantation offer hope and relief from symptoms. Ongoing genetic counseling and support services also help individuals and families manage the psychological and social impacts of the disease.

While Sickle Cell Disease presents significant challenges and impacts quality of life, advances in treatment and ongoing research offer hope for improved outcomes. Management strategies aim to alleviate symptoms, prevent complications, and enhance overall quality of life for individuals affected by this complex genetic disorder.

Looking forward continued research into genetic therapies and new treatment modalities holds promise for further improving the quality of life and life expectancy of individuals living with Sickle Cell Disease. Efforts to raise awareness, expand access to healthcare, and support affected communities globally are crucial in addressing the complex challenges posed by this inherited blood disorder.

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